

THE IMPORTANCE OF STUDYING AND ANALYZING LITERARY TEXTS.

Mukhtorova Rakhimakhon Vokhidjan kizi

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The basis of the creation of the artistic text is the elements of the artistic style. The artistic style has a unique position among the functional styles of the Uzbek language, and at the same time, it also has its own standards. The main feature of the artistic style is the wide range of possibilities to cover language material, the use of all the linguistic units that exist in the national language, the elements characteristic of other functional styles, and the fact that they serve an important task to fulfill an artistic-aesthetic task. Also, in the artistic style, in particular, in poetic speech, a number of words that do not meet the requirements of the current literary orthographic standard are used. In this style, artistic tools such as metaphor, metonymy, synecdoche, and exaggeration are widely used. In Uzbek linguistics, serious research has been carried out in the field of artistic text research.

The linguist M. Yudashev puts forward the following points about the principles of analyzing the artistic text:

1. The principle of unity of form and content.
2. The principle of space and time unity.
3. The principle of determining the relationship of the language of the literary text to the national language and the literary language.
4. Principles of identifying poetic actualized language tools in the literary text.
5. The principle of determining the mechanisms of intertextuality in the literary text.

1. The principle of unity of form and content. One of the types of connection between things and events in existence is the unity of form and content. The concept of the relationship between form and content is a necessary factor for any text. Philosophers evaluate the content as "a set of internal elements and changes that characterize certain things and events." They interpret the form as "a way of expressing the content, an organizer".

Form and content are so intertwined that a perceived defect in one can undermine the integrity of the other. It is clear that if the form and content match, the author's intention will not be fully expressed. Focusing on the balance between the text and its genre characteristics, the issue of compatibility with the nature of the linguistic units in the text should not be overlooked. In a literary text,

the author's skill in shaping the content, individual characteristics in it are of particular value. In the literary text, first of all, this aspect, that is, the unity of form and content, should be considered as the primary principle. Open or hidden compatibility of form and content is a serious ground for the clear and complete manifestation of the author's artistic intention. 2. The principle of space and time unity. When examining the linguistic features of a literary text, it is necessary to approach each event in it taking into account the concept of unity of space and time. Any work is created in relation to time and space. The language of the work on the historical theme includes lexical-grammatical units that clarify in what place and in what environment the events that carry the spirit of a certain time are taking place. The concept of the unity of space and time is not only a feature of a work of art. It applies to any text view. When conducting an analysis based on this principle, one of the diachronic and synchronic aspects should be chosen depending on the period in which the text was written, the topic raised in the text, and the nature of the text units. 3. The principle of determining the relationship of the language of the literary text to the national language and the literary language. Another principle is to consider the relationship of the language of the analyzed text to the vernacular and the literary language.

As stated by V.V. Vinogradov in his work "On the Language of Fiction" (1959), the historical movement of the language of fiction cannot be studied in isolation from the history of the national language and its various branchings. Two types of artistic text can be distinguished: 1) modern text (created today), 2) historical text (created in the past). In turn, two types of modern text can be observed, namely: a) modern text on today's topic; b) a modern text on a historical topic. For example, S.Ahmad's story "Azrail's Past Ways" is a modern text on today's topic, M.Ali's novel "The Great Kingdom" is a modern text on a historical topic, and Navoi's work "Farhad and Shirin" is a historical text. 4. The principle of identifying poetic actualized language tools in the literary text. Determining the poetic actualized language tools in the work of art is also one of the important principles. By revealing the linguistic and artistic essence of such tools, it is possible to clearly imagine the mechanisms of formation and expression of artistic content.

5. The principle of determining the linguistic and semantic features of the mechanisms of intertextuality in the literary text. To determine the other text forms used in the text (such as parables, imitations, narrations, hadiths, narrations, myths, legends, didactems, works or fragments of this or that creator) and to what extent they are compatible with the content of the work, It is extremely necessary to think about the place in the expression of the artistic

content, the important situations in the linguistic and semantic connection with the main text, in opening the linguopoetics of the artistic text. M. Yoldoshev, who has conducted serious research in the field of literary text research in Uzbek linguistics, lists the following methods of literary text analysis:

1. Linguistic conversion method.
2. Method of comparing text options.
3. Method based on dictionaries.
4. The method of creating an index of linguistic units.

1. Linguistic conversion method. Tabdil means "to replace, to change, to replace". In some literature, it can also be used to refer to the use of cognate words in pairs. The results of this analysis method are used to determine the artistry of the language of the work, believability, authorship of the writer. It is intended to reorganize the words or phrases and sentences used in the work, to replace them with similar ones, and to give an assessment on this basis.

2. Method of comparing text options. Through this method, the text of a certain work is compared with other variants, and the essence of the linguistic difference is explained in relation to the writer's point of view, artistic-aesthetic intention and the idea of the work. This method is effective in studying the writer's work on the language of the artistic work, in determining the writer's corrections and different means of expressing the same content, and in general in determining the writer's skill in using language.

3. Method of comparing text options. When checking the language of the work, especially the language features of works or translated works on historical topics, it is necessary to refer to appropriate dictionaries. For example, knowing the meaning of military terms such as gudar, savash, sovut, sadok, ghul, tuv, bayadoq used in the language of the "Shaybani Khan" epic helps to study the work carefully. J. Lapasov's manual entitled "Artistic Text and Linguistic Analysis" contains examples of creating a dictionary of a specific artistic text and important instructions for working on the dictionary. As the scientist rightly noted: "It is difficult to imagine the linguistic analysis of a literary text without various dictionaries. Working on the dictionary is one of the most important factors in developing the vocabulary, oral and written speech of students and students, and with the help of this dictionary, not only the basic meaning of words, but also The meanings of each word, which language element it is, etymology (the history of the origin and gradual development of the word), its structure, and sometimes its grammatical form are intimately acquainted with. In the process of linguopoetic

analysis of the literary text, it is required to create an index of linguistic unity in the work.

The text is a form of speech, and in terms of its function, it is a complete speech unit. Each text has a complex structure and content, and it is an example of oral and written creativity. According to their structure, texts consist of a sentence, a complex syntactic unit, the beginning of a letter, a paragraph, a chapter, a section, and a part. These units are involved in the formation of the text and play an important role in its formation. Each text carries a certain content and conveys different information according to its characteristics. Texts are in the form of artistic text, journalistic text, scientific text, and official text according to the way they convey various information. Imagery and emotionality are the main features of the artistic text.

Its main purpose is to "contribute to the works aimed at determining the links that express the meaningful relationship between the scientific text and its units, their specific characteristics and functions, to determine the author's special relationship in the scientific text and its types." In his candidate's thesis, he studied in detail the syntagmatic and pragmatic features of the Uzbek scientific text on the basis of rich factual materials. M. Hakimov, in his doctoral dissertation on the pragmatic interpretation of the Uzbek language text, studied the text based on linguistic pragmatics, the theory of the speech act formed in Western philosophical linguistics, and showed the specific laws of the overt and hidden contents expressed in the text. gave concrete rules for their semantic, syntactic, presuppositional and pragmatic mechanisms. In the dissertation, the problems of text linguistics in the Uzbek language were theoretically clarified, and a number of completely new ideas were put forward. In the following years, a number of scientific articles related to the study of this or that aspect of the text issue in Uzbek linguistics were also published. But whether it is a natural result of regular and intense scientific researches and researches conducted all over the world, it is widely recognized that such a direction has been formed as a separate science and educational subject, and no one denies it. does not

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